

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Oxidation of Aryl Methyl Sulphides with Pyridinium Dichromate

G. MANGALAM* and SUBBIAH MEENAKSHI SUNDARAM

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Engineering & Technology, Annamalai University, Annamalainagar-608 002

Manuscript received 7 November 1989, revised 24 August 1990, accepted 26 January 1991

Kinetics of the oxidation of aryl methyl sulphides (CH_3SAr) with PDC yielding sulphoxides were investigated in aqueous acetic acid medium. The rate equation, $v = k [\text{sulphide}][\text{oxidant}]$ was found to be valid. The observed substituent effect is explained by an electrophilic attack of PDC oxygen on sulphide, leading to a polar transition state. The reaction did not induce polymerisation of acrylonitrile. Addition of Mn^{II} decreased the rate considerably indicating the involvement of transient species. Decomposition of the complex formed between the sulphide and oxidant was assumed as the rate-determining step. On the basis of the results, a suitable mechanism has been proposed

THE mechanisms of the oxidation of sulphides to sulphoxides involving polar transition states have been studied extensively. Pyridinium dichromate (PDC)¹ is reported to be neutral and mild oxidant for selective oxidation. The results of the kinetics of oxidation of sulphides by PDC indicate that the oxidation by PDC and $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ ² follows different mechanistic pathways. The present paper deals with the kinetics of oxidation of some *meta*- and *para*-substituted aryl methyl sulphides by PDC.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Pyridinium dichromate (PDC) was synthesised by the method described in literature¹. All the aryl methyl sulphides were prepared by reported methods^{3,4}. The purity was checked by spectroscopic methods and tlc. Acetic acid used as solvent was purified (to 99.9%) before use.

Kinetic measurement: The reactions were performed under pseudo-first order conditions by maintaining a large excess of the sulphides over PDC. The reaction mixture was homogeneous throughout the reaction. The reactions were followed by monitoring the decrease in absorption of PDC at 446 nm employing a Jasco 7200 spectrophotometer with a variable-temperature accessory. In the case of nitro compounds, the reactions were followed iodometrically. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants obtained by the two methods agreed within $\pm 3\%$. Computations of the rate constants were made from the plot of $\log [\text{PDC}]$ against time. All rate constants are the average of two or more determinations.

Product analysis: In kinetic mixtures, after 80% completion of the reaction, the products were isolated by extracting with chloroform, washed with water, dried with anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and the solvent

evaporated. The residue thus obtained and the authentic samples of sulphide, sulphoxide and sulphone were applied on the same plate. It was developed and spots were identified by exposure to iodine. The solvent system employed was benzene-ethanol (80 : 20, v/v) mixture. The reaction mixture showed spots at the same heights (same R_f values) as those of the authentic samples of sulphides and sulphoxides only.

Results and Discussion

The stoichiometric runs carried out in presence of excess PDC at 35° reveal that 2 mol of the oxidant are consumed by 3 mol of sulphide.

The experiments were carried out with 60% (v/v) acetic acid. The kinetics of the reactions was studied with $[\text{PDC}] = 3.7 - 15.2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[\text{sulphide}] = 1.3 - 4 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. Plots of $\log [\text{PDC}]$ vs time were found to be linear indicating a first order dependence on $[\text{PDC}]$. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_1), calculated from the slopes of the plots were found to be independent of the initial concentration of PDC. At higher $[\text{PDC}]$, the rate constant decreased with increasing Cr^{VI} concentration (Table 1). This observation is well-explained by Wiberg⁵. As the concentration of Cr^{VI} is increased a progressively smaller portion of the total amount is in the form of acid chromate ion and the rate constant decreased with increasing Cr^{VI} concentration. Variation of $[\text{sulphide}]$ at a fixed concentration of PDC was found to increase the rate constant. A plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [\text{sulphide}]$ gave a straight line with a slope equal to 1.02. This was further demonstrated by the constancy of k_2 ($k_2 = k_1 / [\text{sulphide}]$) (Table 1). Plot of $1/k_1$ vs $1/[\text{S}]$ was found to be linear ($r = 0.99$) with a negligible intercept on the ordinate.

The rates were found to increase with the increase in the percentage of acetic acid, i.e. with decreasing

TABLE 1—RATE DATA FOR OXIDATION
Temp. = 35 ± 0.1°; HOAc : H₂O = 60 : 40

[Sulphide] × 10 ⁻³ M	[PDC] × 10 ⁻⁴ M	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	k ₂ × 10 ³ M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
2.7	3.7	9.63	3.58
2.7	5.7	9.96	3.70
2.7	7.6	9.85	3.66
2.7	9.5	9.63	3.58
2.7	11.4	9.94	3.69
2.7	13.3	8.90	3.31
2.7	15.2	8.59	3.19
1.3	11.4	4.58	3.40
2.0	11.4	7.24	3.59
2.7	11.4	9.94	3.69
3.4	11.4	11.80	3.51
4.0	11.4	14.07	3.49

dielectric constant of the solvent mixture (Table 2). This enhanced oxidising ability is attributed to the formation of acetochromate ion. The acetyl group enhances the electron-accepting power of chromium, thereby facilitating the reaction. Effect of ionic strength was studied by adding NaClO₄ (Table 3). The rate was affected only to a small extent indicating that the reaction involves an ion and dipole.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SOLVENT COMPOSITION
[Sulphide] = 1.3 × 10⁻³ M, [PDC] = 11.4 × 10⁻⁴ M

HOAc : H ₂ O % (v/v)	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	k ₂ × 10 ³ M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
60 : 40	4.58	3.41
70 : 30	8.99	6.68
75 : 25	14.70	10.93
80 : 20	25.65	19.08
90 : 10	57.93	43.09

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF IONIC STRENGTH
[Sulphide] = 2.7 × 10⁻³ M, [PDC] = 11.4 × 10⁻⁴ M, HOAc : H₂O = 60 : 40 (v/v)

[NaClO ₄] × 10 ⁻⁴ M	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	k ₂ × 10 ³ M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
0.0	9.94	3.69
3.8	8.58	3.19
7.6	8.47	3.15
15.3	7.95	2.96
22.9	8.34	3.10
30.6	8.35	3.10

To have some idea whether the reaction takes place by one electron or two-electron transfer process, the effect of Mn^{II} was studied. It was found that increase in concentration of Mn^{II} decreased the rate considerably (Table 4). A two-electron transfer process will result in the formation of Cr^{IV} and addition of Mn^{II} removes the Cr^{IV} formed⁶. So it is possible that the reaction involves a two-electron transfer process. Also the absence of polymerisation when acrylonitrile was added to the reaction mixture, rules out a one-electron oxidation giving rise to free radicals.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF Mn^{II}

[Sulphide] = 2.7 × 10⁻³ M, [PDC] = 11.4 × 10⁻⁴ M

[Mn ^{II}] × 10 ⁻³ M	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	k ₂ × 10 ³ M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
0.0	9.94	3.69
0.2	3.99	1.49
1.3	1.84	0.69
1.7	1.61	0.60

Rate law :

The above mechanism leads to the following rate equation,

$$-d[\text{PDC}]/dt = k_2[\text{Complex}] = k_2K[\text{PDC}][\text{Sulphide}]$$

$$\text{Rate} = k[\text{PDC}][\text{Sulphide}]$$

where, $k = k_2K$. Study of induced oxidation suggests that the rate-controlling reaction produces tetravalent chromium. So it is reasonable to assume the decomposition of the complex as the rate-limiting step.

Effect of substituents : The effect of substituents on the rate of oxidation has been studied by employing a number of *meta*- and *para*-substituted phenyl methyl sulphides. The rate of the reaction is accelerated by electron-releasing substituents and retarded by electron-withdrawing ones (Table 5).

TABLE 5—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS AND ENTHALPY AND ENTROPY OF ACTIVATION

[PDC] = 11.4 × 10⁻⁴ M, HOAc : H₂O = 60 : 40 (v/v)

Substituent	k ₂ × 10 ³ M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹			ΔH* kJ mol ⁻¹	-ΔS* JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
	25°	35°	45°		
<i>p</i> -MeO	14.6	22.0	33.4	30.2	160.0
<i>p</i> -Me	5.0	8.8	12.3	33.0	159.0
<i>p</i> -H	2.2	3.6	5.3	31.5	171.0
<i>p</i> -Cl	1.0	1.5	2.5	32.8	173.2
<i>p</i> -Br	0.6	0.9	1.3	28.0	193.8
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	0.03	0.07	0.12	40.8	173.4
<i>m</i> -Me	2.6	3.8	5.5	28.0	190.3
<i>m</i> -Cl	0.5	0.7	1.2	30.7	186.2
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	0.10	0.16	0.24	32.0	195.5

Correlation analysis : The reactivity pattern is brought out by two different correlations at 35°, one of log k₂ with σ and the other of log k₂ with σ⁺ and/or σ⁻ correlation^{7,8}. In some reactions^{4,9,10} involving sulphur centre, both σ⁺ and σ⁻ have been employed simultaneously in correlation analysis. Though a satisfactory correlation is obtained with σ⁺ and/or σ⁻ values (ρ = -1.35, r = 0.978, s = 0.17) a good correlation is found to exist when Hammett σ constants are plotted against log k₂ (ρ = -2.13, r = 0.989, s = 0.12) (Fig.1). The negative ρ values indicate an electron-deficient sulphur in the transition state. The ρ values evaluated at three different temperatures (ρ = -2.18, -2.13, -2.09 at 25, 35

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log k_2$ vs σ (at 35°); Hammett plot for substituted phenyl methyl sulphides at 35° ; numbered as in Table 5.

and 45° respectively) are inversely proportional to the temperature as expected¹¹. Generally one-electron transfer process is characterised by low ρ values (-0.5 to -1.5)¹²⁻¹⁴. In this reaction, a ρ value of -2.18 has been considered as an indication of two-electron transfer process. In the oxidation of aryl methyl sulphides by pyridinium chlorochromate (PCC), a two-electron transfer mechanism was proposed ($\rho = -2.12$)¹⁵.

The entropies of activation are largely negative as expected for a bimolecular reaction¹⁶ (Table 5). One of the prerequisites for a reaction to obey the Hammett equation is that it should be isentropic^{17,18}. The entropies of activation (Table 3) in our case are negative but they do not remain constant. In such cases, the variation in ΔS^\ddagger should be linearly related to changes in ΔH^\ddagger by the equation^{19,20},

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = \Delta H_0 + \beta \Delta S^\ddagger$$

where β is the isokinetic temperature. However, Exner^{21,22} criticised the validity of such a linear correlation between ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger as these quantities are dependent on each other. The experimental data can be treated by the equation^{23,24},

$$\log (k_2)_{T_2} = a + b \log (k_2)_{T_1}$$

where, $T_2 > T_1$. Using the above equation an excellent correlation ($r = 0.999$, $s = 0.03$) was obtained when $\log (k_2)_{45^\circ}$ was plotted against $\log (k_2)_{35^\circ}$. The excellent correlation serves as an argument that the reaction follows a common mechanism. Entropies of activation are close to the values observed in typical reactions involving oxygen transfer¹⁵.

Mechanism: In aqueous solutions of Cr^{VI} at concentrations lesser than $0.05M$, the monomeric

form predominates²⁵. In the present investigation the oxidant concentration is very low and under this condition active oxidising species is HCrO_4^- .

The experimental results can be accounted in terms of a mechanism involving oxygen transfer from PDC to sulphide similar to the mechanism suggested for the oxidation of sulphides by pyridinium chlorochromate¹⁵. Electron transfer from sulphur to Cr^{VI} occurs, resulting in the formation of a polar transition state. In diacetyl chromate oxidation of diphenyl sulphide, when the oxygen was labelled with ^{18}O at the $\text{Cr}=\text{O}$ group, complete oxygen transfer was observed by Wiberg and Lapse²⁶,

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Comparison with similar oxidants: PDC is found to proceed by a non-radical polar mechanism, whereas the available literature on $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ oxidation of methyl phenyl sulphide shows that the reaction follows a free radical mechanism involving the formation of cation radical as the reaction intermediate.

Comparing the results of oxidation of aryl methyl sulphides by PCC¹⁵ with those of the present investigation, it is found that these two oxidants behave similarly: (i) the reactions exhibit non-radical overall second order kinetics, (ii) both are characterised by a low enthalpy of activation and an appreciable negative entropy of activation and (iii) the rate-determining step involves a two-electron transfer process.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Dr. AN. Andiappan, Dean, Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Annamalai University, and to Dr. S. Govindasamy, Professor of Chemistry, for facilities.

References

1. E. J. COREY and G. SCHMIDT, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1979, **5**, 999.
2. C. SRINIVASAN, A. CHELLAMANI and S. RAJAGOPAL, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1985, **50**, 1201.
3. N. ARUMUGAM, C. SRINIVASAN and P. KUTHALINGAM, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1978, **16**, 478.
4. C. SRINIVASAN, P. KUTHALINGAM and N. ARUMUGAM, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1978, **56**, 3043.
5. "Oxidations in Organic Chemistry", ed. K. B. WIBERG, Academic, New York, 1965, p. 78.
6. G. T. E. GRAHAM and F. H. WESTHEIMER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 3030.
7. J. SHORTER, "Correlation Analysis of Organic Reactivity", Research Studies, 1982, p. 30.
8. H. C. BROWN and OKAMOTO, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 4979.
9. O. EXNER in "Advances in Linear Free Energy Relationships", eds. N. B. CHAPMAN and J. SHORTER, Plenum, New York, 1972, p. 34.
10. L. D. PETTIT, A. ROYSTON and R. J. WHEWELL, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 2009.
11. H. H. JAFFE, *Chem. Rev.*, 1953, **53**, 191.
12. P. D. BARTLETT and C. RUCHARDT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 1756.
13. G. A. RUSSELL and R. C. WILLIAMSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 2357; R. L. HUANG and K. H. LEE, *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1966, 935.
14. V. BALIAH and P. V. V. SATYANARAYANA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1978, **16**, 686.
15. K. RAJASREKARAN, T. BASKARAN and C. GNANASEKARAN, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1984, 1183.
16. A. FROST and R. G. PHARSON, "Kinetics and Mechanism", Wiley, New York, 1961, p. 144.
17. P. R. WELLS, *Chem. Rev.*, 1963, **63**, 171.
18. J. E. LEFFLER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1955, **20**, 1202.
19. J. E. LEFFLER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1955, **23**, 2199.
20. R. C. PETERSON, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, **29**, 3133.
21. O. EXNER, *Nature*, 1964, **201**, 488.
22. V. A. PALM and R. V. VIZZERT, *Dokl. Akad. Nauk. USSR*, 1962, **142**, 1091.
23. M. J. MALAWSKI, *Roczniki Chem.*, 1964, **38**, 1129.
24. D. H. GESKE, J. L. RAGLE, M. A. BAMBERG and A. L. BALCH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **86**, 987.
25. "Oxidations in Organic Chemistry", ed. K. B. WIBERG, Academic, New York, 1965, pp. 71, 182.
26. K. B. WIBERG and P. A. LEFSS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 2612.